

CRITICAL CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING THE EXAMINATION OF COMPLEX STABILITY BY JATKAR AND MATTOO

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It has been experimentally demonstrated that the potentiometric titration method of Jatkar and Mattoo yields reliable results only for metals of higher redox potentials. Even in such cases the results are fairly uncertain, and this uncertainty gradually increases proceeding toward the metals of the more negative redox potentials.

When examined spectroscopically the complexes in relation to the mechanism of light absorption, it is important to know the number of intermediate complexes formed and their composition. Consequently, every method, demonstrating the formation of these intermediate complexes and predicting their composition, is significant.

The formation of complexes in consecutive steps can be represented by the equation :

Bjerrum has established a method ("Metalamine formation in aqueous solution", P. Haase and Son, Copenhagen, 1941) of calculating the stability constant of such complexes, while the method demonstrating the intermediate complexes has been worked out by Job (*Ann. chim.*, 1928, 9, 115; Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437).

Any method, including the spectroscopical one, which deals with the study of formation and of composition of intermediate complexes and their stability, is significant. In the present communication the potentiometric method of Jatkar and Mattoo (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 592, 607, 775; 1954, 31, 299) has been thoroughly studied. The essential point in their method relates to the dependence of the formation of different complexes on the concentration of metal ion and of the complex-forming agent. Consequently, if a certain metal ion is potentiometrically titrated with a complex-forming compound in the presence of an indicator electrode, a curve is obtained by plotting the E.M.F. against the concentration of the complex-forming compound, exhibiting breaks or shoulders wherever a complex is formed. Thus, from the concentrations of the complex-forming compound and the metal ion corresponding to the breaks, the composition of the complex formed can be determined.

The principle involved in the titration is based on the p_n change or change in the oxidation potential of the solution. In the former case, where the complex-forming compound is a weak acid, it is assumed that in the formation of the metal complex, one or more of its protons can be replaced by the metal. Bearing in mind the above mentioned titration curve, there appears a break or shoulder when a proton is

released owing to complex formation. This method had been extensively employed by Schwarzenbach *et al.* (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1947, 30, 1798; 1948, 31, 331; 1945, 28, 828), Magrath (*Biochem. J.*, 1947, 41, 534), and Frost and Martell (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 3743). As to the change of oxidation potential, the following considerations have to be taken into account. Assuming that a metal is in equilibrium with the solution of its own ion, the equation is

The oxidation potential of the electrode can be represented by the usual Nernst equation:

$$E = E_0 - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln a$$

where a represents the activity of the metal ion and E is the electrode potential; E_0 , the standard oxidation potential, is the value of E when $a=1$ and is related to K , the thermodynamic equilibrium constant by the equation

$$E_0 = \frac{0.059}{n} \log K.$$

The complex formation with the metal is followed by the decrease of activity of the metal ion and by the increase of the oxidation potential. It has been also experimentally proved that the oxidation potential of the solution is considerably increased in the presence of strong complex-forming agents (Dieth, *Chem. Rev.*, 1937, 21, 39; Ponzio, *Gazzetta*, 1921, 51, 213). Recently Kleinberg (*J. Chem. Ed.*, 1950, 27, 32) cleared up the role of the complex formation in an unusual oxidation state of the metal. The above statements suggested, e.g., that greater part of the known compounds of ions, Ag^{II} and Cu^{III} , is in the form of complexes. Further, it has been demonstrated that the oxidation state depends on the complex-forming agent and its donor group and on the replaceable H atoms, by means of which it is expedient to determine the composition of the complex.

Consequently, the conclusion may be drawn that, in general, the complex formation causes considerable increase of the oxidation potential. Thus, the co-ordination increases the oxidation potential with a donor group, *i.e.*, the relative stability of the higher valence state. Especially it is true if the complex formation occurs with negatively charged donors, e.g. with anions of weak acids.

Jatkar and Mattoo (*loc. cit.*) in order to establish the composition of complexes of Fe^{III} and phenol derivatives, considered the oxidation-reduction potential change as a basis. Their method is, in fact, based on Bezier's measurements (*J. chim. phys.*, 1944, 41, 100) on the electrode potential of Fe^{II}/Fe^{III} when the Fe^{3+} ion is in equilibrium with the complex-forming agent. The method of Jatkar and Mattoo (*loc. cit.*) involves the measurement of the oxidation-reduction potential of ferric ion in the presence of phenol derivatives of different concentrations, employing the following galvanic chain:

The mv's, thus obtained, were plotted against the concentration and the shoulders of the curve denoted the equivalent concentrations of the phenol used for the complex formation. In the authors' opinion these shoulders became sharp peaks in the differential curve when the quotient of the difference in E.M.F. produced by two concentrations and that of the corresponding concentrations were plotted against the concentration, e.g. it was shown that the complexes, $[\text{Fe}(\text{OPh})_2]^{2+} \rightarrow [\text{Fe}(\text{OPh})_6]^{2+}$ between Fe^{3+} and phenol were formed.

As to the figures of Jatkar and Mattoo with reference to the potentiometric titration, the results are too uncertain and scattered to bring out the precise relation of the metal ion and of the complex-forming agent without assuming the possible structure of the complexes.

Although no mention was made as to the reproducibility of their results, the control tests, carried out in this laboratory, proved the contrary. The reason for this is that aqueous solution of FeCl_3 has been employed wherein, especially in excess of acid, chloro-complexes of different composition, for example binuclear Fe_2Cl_6 , appear (Muthmann and Nage, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2010), which has been proved to be analogous to Al_2Cl_6 . (Palmer and Elliot, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 1852; Gerding and Smit, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1941, 50B, 171). In addition to these complexes, a complex anion of FeCl_6^{3-} in hydrochloric acid solution is produced where the halogen atoms are gradually exchanged for water molecules (Schwarz and Mayer, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 166, 190).

Consequently, the authors felt it necessary, in order to eliminate such disturbing effects, to employ perchlorate solution on the basis of the investigations of Jander *et al.* (*Kolloid-Beih.*, 1936, 43, 337) owing to the negligible complex-forming effect of perchlorate ion (Fromherz and Lih, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, 153A, 321). Besides the above mentioned facts, a whole series of oxyhydrate may be produced in consequence of which the potential changes with time. As it has been stated by Bray and Hershey (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1889), the hydrolytic reactions have disturbing effect on the redox potential even if equilibrium occurs.

However, another condition that had not been taken into account by Jatkar and Mattoo is that the concentration of the reduced substance should not be too low, relative to that of the oxidised substance (Sherrill and Haas, *ibid.*, 1936, 58, 952). The measurements of the redox potential, so far carried out, suggest the extreme importance of this fact with the redox-system of $\text{Tl}^+ - \text{Tl}^{2+}$ (Popoff and Kunz, *ibid.*, 1929, 51, 382), $\text{Hg}^+ - \text{Hg}^{2+}$ (Popoff *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1931, 53, 1195) and $\text{Fe}^{2+} - \text{Fe}^{3+}$ (Schumb and Sweetzer, *ibid.*, 1935, 57, 871). The present authors, at any rate, started from pure Fe^{3+} solution, although it is known that reduction occurs in consequence of the effect of light, especially of U.V. rays (Kiss A, M.T.A. közleményei, 6, 37; Rabinovitsch and Stockmayer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 234), as follows: $\text{Fe}^{3+} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} + h\nu = \text{Fe}^{2+} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}^+$. As demonstrated by Weiss and Porret (*Nature*, 1937, 139, 1019) in the case of ceric ions, the concentration of reduced substance produced under common conditions owing to the effect of visible light may be considerably low.

TABLE I

Cu ²⁺ .	Anion.	Cu: anion.	Cu ²⁺ .	Anion.	Cu: anion.
With H ₃ PO ₄ .			With citric acid.		
0.009615 c.c.	0.003846 c.c.	5: 2	0.009756 c.c.	0.002439 c.c.	4: 1
0.008547	0.01453	2: 3	0.007782	0.02218	2: 5
0.007634	0.02366	1: 3	0.007017	0.02982	1: 4
0.007092	0.02908	1: 4	0.006473	0.03527	1: 5
0.005988	0.04012	2: 13	0.005682	0.04318	1: 15
With sulphanic acid.			With HNO ₃ .		
0.008511	0.001490	11: 2	0.008368	0.01632	1: 2
0.007843	0.002156	7: 2	0.006969	0.03031	1: 4
0.007220	0.002780	5: 2	0.006557	0.03443	1: 5
0.006667	0.003333	2: 1	0.005634	0.04366	2: 15
0.006192	0.003808	3: 2	With H ₃ BO ₃ .		
0.005525	0.004476	1: 1	0.002343	0.001961	1: 1
			0.002183	0.008676	1: 4
			0.002061	0.013790	2: 13

The following complex composition, as represented in Figs. 1-5, were evaluated from the data represented in Table I. The experimental data prove that the real composition

FIG. 1

of the single intermediary complexes cannot be obtained and the evaluation is uncertain. That is to say, all the difficulties rendering uncertain the measurement in case of Fe³⁺ ion were also felt by us. Moreover, the *p_H* change of the solution exerts partly

an influence on the potential beside the oxidation process proper. This might be eliminated by using the proper metal electrodes. This, however, would limit the

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

area of utilisation, as every metal does not yield a well-defined potential between the metal and the solution due to the slight oxidisability of the surface of the metal.

Comparing our data, measured for Cu²⁺ ion, with those of Jatkar and Matteo, made with Fe³⁺ ion, the following interesting conclusion can be drawn. The data referring to titration curve of Cu²⁺ are more uncertain and are more scattered than those referring to Fe³⁺ ion. Comparing the redox potentials of the ions [(Pt)Cu²⁺/Cu⁺

+ 0.159; (Pt)Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺: + 0.783; Körtum and Bockris, "Textbook of Electrochemistry", 1951, New York, p. 262], "it becomes evident that the value of Cu²⁺/Cu⁺ system is less than that of Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺ system, leading to the conclusion that the more positive the redox potential, the more reliable are the data.

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

EXPERIMENTAL

As used by Jatkar and Mattoo (*loc. cit.*), a 25 c.c. burette, a 200 c.c. titrating vessel and a galvanic chain were used for the titration. To measure the mv change the Hartmann and Braun "Pehavi" compensator was employed. In every case the

following method was carried out: The solution (20 c.c.) containing metal ion was pipetted into the titrating vessel and stirred with a glass rod at 500 r.p.m. for 15 minutes and the starting potential was read. The titrating acid was then added in portions of 0.25 c.c., and one minute after each addition the mv value was read. The one minute interval was essential as it was noticed that the potential change occurred also without titration (23 mv in 2 hours) due to the above mentioned reasons.

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